

Climate Change and Resource Based Conflict: A Study of Farmer/Herder Conflict in Omala Local Government Area of Kogi State, Nigeria

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PAPER KEYWORDS

Climate Change, Conflict, Resource-based, Omala, Push Factor.

ABSTRACT

Desertification in the core northern states of Nigeria is yielding undesired results. Natural phenomena and man-made factors have contributed to climate change. Thus, the necessity to survive made the herders move to the green belt of central Nigeria, particularly along the Niger-Benue River valley, in which the Omala Local Government Area is situated. The desire to use the limited resources, such as land, by the people of Omala and the herders has led to violent clashes. Although there have been policies and interventions from the government to encourage the provision of franchises and to promote afforestation in the affected areas, these policies and interventions have not yielded positive results; instead, the conflicts keep lingering. To understand the extent to which this resources-based conflict has caused economic and social losses, the study, which is anchored on the environmental scarcity theory, adopted the survey research design and selected a sample of 399 from the total population of 108,402 using the Taro Yamane approach. The questionnaires used in the collection of data were closed-ended, and they were distributed using the simple random technique. The study found, among other things, that the conflict is resource-based and Omala has suffered a lot of losses to the point of deserting some villages. This has limited their farming activities due to fear of further reducing the food supply. The study recommended that the policy of ranching and afforestation should be taken seriously by the government to curb this violence and restore peace to the local government area.

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1.1. Introduction

Climate change has emerged as one of the most pressing environmental challenges of the 21st century, with significant implications for socio-economic activities and human security across the globe. It involves long-term shifts in temperature, rainfall patterns, and other climatic conditions, largely driven by human activities such as deforestation, greenhouse gas emissions, and unsustainable land use (United Nations, 2020; IPCC, 2022). In many parts of Africa, including Nigeria, climate change has altered ecological systems and exacerbated environmental degradation, leading to reduced availability of water, pastureland, and fertile soils (United Nations in Nigeria, 2020). These environmental shifts have intensified competition over scarce natural resources and heightened vulnerability among rural populations whose livelihoods depend on agriculture and pastoralism.

In Nigeria, the farmer–herder conflict has become a recurrent and deadly source of violence, particularly in Middle Belt states where agricultural and grazing zones intersect. Traditionally, herders practice transhumance, seasonally moving livestock in search of pasture and water. However, climate-related changes such as drought, desertification, and erratic rainfall have reduced available grazing land in the northern regions, forcing herders to migrate further south into agrarian territories (Okpara & Onwuchekwa, 2025). This southward movement has increased encounters and friction between herders and sedentary farmers, leading to frequent clashes over land, water, and crop damage (Okpara & Onwuchekwa, 2025). As both groups compete for dwindling resources, what were once manageable disputes have escalated into widespread conflicts with serious humanitarian, socio-economic and security implications.

Empirical studies increasingly link climate change with the intensification of these resource-based conflicts. Research indicates that climate-induced scarcity of grazing land and water disrupts traditional migratory routes and intensifies competition between farmers and herders (Efobi, Adejumo & Kim, 2025). Moreover, demographic pressures and agricultural expansion further amplify resource competition, compounding tensions in resource-scarce environments (Ogayi & Agada, 2025; Nukoaka Lebari et al., 2022). Despite some scholarly debate about the direct causal relationship between climate change and conflict, there is growing evidence that environmental stress acts as a “threat multiplier”, exacerbating existing socio-economic grievances and structural vulnerabilities, particularly in regions like Kogi State’s Omala Local Government Area.

The prominence of farmer–herder conflicts demonstrates the complex interplay between environmental change and social conflict in Nigeria. In Omala Local Government Area of Kogi State, this dynamic is particularly relevant as both farming and pastoral communities vie for limited land and water resources under changing climatic conditions. Although the Nigerian government has proposed different solutions, such as afforestation policies and the provision of ranches, these have not solved the problem. The constant killings of the people of Omala by the herders and the reduction in farming activities due to the fear of being killed on the farm have remained high. The knowledge of the role of climate change in shaping resource-based conflict is therefore crucial for developing sustainable strategies that can address both environmental vulnerability and communal peace.

Literature Review

Climate Change

Climate change refers to long-term alterations in average weather patterns, including changes in temperature, rainfall, wind systems, and the frequency of extreme weather events, occurring over extended periods. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2022), climate change is primarily driven by human activities such as the burning of fossil fuels, deforestation, and unsustainable land use, which increase greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere. In developing countries, climate change manifests through droughts, desertification, flooding, and erratic rainfall, all of which directly affect agricultural productivity and natural resource

availability. In Nigeria, these climate-induced environmental changes have heightened pressure on land and water resources, thereby increasing competition among resource-dependent communities

Conflict

Conflict is a multidimensional social phenomenon involving perceived or actual incompatibilities between individuals, groups, or states over goals, interests, or values. Deutsch (1973) defines it as a situation in which incompatible activities occur or are perceived to occur, while Thomas (1992) emphasises that conflict begins when one party perceives that another may frustrate a concern of theirs. Conflict can occur at different levels: intrapersonal, interpersonal, intergroup, organisational, and political, with intergroup conflict being most relevant in agrarian settings.

Causes of conflict are multifaceted. Resource scarcity, particularly due to environmental stress and climate-induced desertification, drives competition over land and water, often leading to disputes between farmers and pastoralists (Homer-Dixon, 1999; Abbass, 2012; Blench, 2010). Beyond ecological factors, power struggles and the quest for dominance contribute to conflicts, as groups assert control over land or political authority (Benjaminsen et al., 2012; Mustapha, 2014). Political manipulation and governance failures can exacerbate tensions, allowing conflicts to persist unchecked (Fayemi, 2018). Conflict can be constructive, promoting problem-solving and cooperation, or destructive, causing violence, loss of life, and social disruption. In contexts like farmer–herder relations in Nigeria, conflicts are often destructive, threatening livelihoods and social stability. Understanding conflict conceptually is crucial for developing strategies that mitigate its adverse effects while promoting peaceful coexistence.

Resource-Based Conflict

Resource-based conflict refers to disputes and violent confrontations arising from competition over the access, control, and use of natural resources such as land, water, forests, and grazing fields. Scholars argue that such conflicts are often intensified where resources are scarce, unevenly distributed, or poorly governed (Homer-Dixon, 1999; Collier & Hoeffler, 2004). Resource-based conflicts are particularly prevalent in agrarian societies where livelihoods depend heavily on natural resources. In many African contexts, including Nigeria, these conflicts are exacerbated by population growth, environmental degradation, weak institutions, and identity politics. Resource-based conflict may be both a cause and consequence of underdevelopment, as it disrupts livelihoods, weakens social cohesion, and undermines governance structures.

Farmer–Herder Conflict

Farmer–herder conflict refers to recurrent clashes between sedentary farming communities and nomadic or semi-nomadic pastoralists, primarily over access to land, water, and grazing routes. Traditionally, farmers and herders maintained symbiotic relationships; however, changing climatic conditions, population pressure, agricultural expansion, and the breakdown of traditional conflict-resolution mechanisms have intensified these disputes (Blench, 2010; Benjaminsen et al., 2012). In Nigeria, farmer–herder conflicts have become increasingly violent, particularly in the Middle Belt

region, where declining pasture availability and southward migration of herders intersect with farming activities. These conflicts are often resource-based but are further complicated by ethnic, religious, and political dimensions, making them a significant threat to rural security, food production, and social stability.

Empirical literature

The nexus between climate change and farmer–herder conflict has increasingly attracted scholarly attention as environmental stressors intensify competition for land and water resources in agrarian economies. Researchers have empirically examined how climate variability triggers migration, alters livelihoods, and escalates disputes between herders and sedentary farmers in Nigeria and other African contexts. Efobi, et al (2025) examined climate Change and the Farmer-Pastoralist’s Violent Conflict. A pre-registered survey experiment was conducted with 550 residents in conflict-prone areas to understand how exposure to climate change narratives affects support for policy responses. The study found that when residents perceive herders’ migration as driven by climate change, they are more likely to support inclusive policies integrating herders into local communities. Perceived climate vulnerability increases tolerance and reduces hostility. The study concluded that climate change narratives can shape conflict attitudes and foster more accommodative policy preferences, suggesting that public understanding of climate drivers may be important for peaceful coexistence.

Similarly, Oluwatayo & Ojo (2025) examined climate change-induced conflicts in rural Nigeria, with the objective of identifying determinants of herder–arable crop farmer conflict in Ekiti State amid climate-related stressors. The study used a multistage sampling technique to survey 220 smallholder farmers, analysed via descriptive statistics and a probit regression model. Conflict drivers were found to include socio-economic factors such as age, education, farming experience, credit access, and farm location. The study also found that climate change manifested through drought and forage scarcity, which was associated with herders’ southward movement and resulting crop destruction. Ogbogu & Eze (2025) explored how climate-induced migration influences the frequency of farmer–herder conflicts and proposed strategies for peace. The study used secondary data analysis framed within a socio-ecological system theory and drew on literature and policy reports to explore environmental and socio-economic drivers of conflict. The study found that climate change has significantly reduced crop yields and grazing land, altering migration patterns and intensifying land competition. Adaptive strategies, including integrated land-use planning and adaptive frameworks, were recommended by the study. The study concluded that sustainable peace depended on integrated climate adaptation, environmental governance, and community-led conflict resolution strategies.

Obikaeze et al. (2023) assessed how conflicts over farmland impacted human and food security in Nigeria. Secondary analysis using environmental/resource scarcity theory was used, and findings revealed that the struggle over farmland, driven by environmental changes and livelihood pressures, threatens food security, with frequent clashes resulting in loss of life and displacement. The study concluded that addressing resource scarcity and ensuring equitable access to land were crucial for mitigating conflict and securing rural livelihoods.

Okeize (2021) examined spatial correlations between climate change vulnerability and farmer–herder conflict across Nigeria. The study adopted geospatial analysis of climatic, environmental, and conflict data across regions to map conflict hotspots. Climate vulnerability areas do not always correlate negatively with conflict intensity, implying that climate change alone may not fully explain conflict patterns absent other social and identity factors. The study concluded that the climate change–conflict link is complex and policies must consider identity, governance, and local dynamics alongside environmental stress.

Okpara & Onwuchekwa (2023) considered how Nigeria’s Climate Change Act could mitigate farmer–herder conflicts. A doctrinal literature review of climate change policies and conflict frameworks was done, and the study found that legislative frameworks exist but are weakly implemented, and effective enforcement could reduce climate pressures that fuel conflict.

Gansler (2013) in “Nigeria: The politicized herders and farmers conflict” opined that the herder farmers conflict in Nigeria is more of a political battle and the desire by a set of groups to conquer another group. The nature of the conflict has escalated beyond what it used to be. The use of weapons and harmful instruments characterizes this form of crisis, which makes it more political than it used to be. The study of Gansler gives another view or presents another way in which this crisis can be analyzed. Although this work is relevant to this study, it failed to consider the role of climate change as a major push factor in causing this conflict in the Omala Local Government of Kogi State, Nigeria.

Abass (2014), “No Retreat No Surrender Conflict for Survival Between Fulani Pastoralists and Farmers in Northern Nigeria”, explained the situation of the crisis between the herders and farmers in the North. The North happens to be a place where herders are many. They only migrate to the other parts of the country during the dry season when pastures are no longer available for their cattle. The crisis between herders and farmers has degenerated into another form of conflict that has claimed lives and threatened the peace of the nation as a whole. This study is relevant because the and explains the threat the herders and farmers crisis poses to the security of the nation. The study, however, failed to address the case of Omala local government area in Kogi State.

Maiangwa (2017) in “Conflicting Indignity and Farmer–Herder Conflicts in Postcolonial Africa” examined the cases of herders and farmers’ crisis in Africa. The study posits that the crisis between herders and farmers exists in Africa, and this crisis is mainly a result of competition for resources and a case of misunderstanding. Also, the struggle to take over more lands could also account for the existence of the crisis. Regardless of which caused the crisis, the existence of the crisis affects peace and has a disastrous impact.

Idakwoji et al (2018) worked on a study titled “Herdsman/Farmers Conflict in Kogi State: Security and Developmental Implications, which investigated the conflict between migrant Fulani herders and the farmers in Omala Local Government Area of Kogi State and found the situation to be alarming. According to this work, the conflict has claimed lives, destroyed properties and has also created fear in the minds of the people in the Local Government Area. This work is related to this study because it not

only examines the effect of insecurity posed by the migrant Fulani herdsmen on the people and the community, but it also considers Kogi State.

Oladipo (2018), while discussing the problems posed by the herders under the headline “25 Killed as Herdsmen Attack Kogi Communities,” explained the role the migrant Fulani herders played in the killing of not less than 25 people in some communities in Kogi State. The activities of the migrant Fulani herdsmen and the conflict that occurred with the people in the communities led to the death of at least 25 people, not to mention the properties that were lost. This work is also related to this study because it discusses the effect of insecurity posed by the migrant Fulani herdsmen on the people and the communities in Kogi State.

Gaps in Literature

Climate change acts as a threat multiplier within the Environmental Scarcity framework. Rising temperatures, unpredictable rainfall patterns, flooding, and prolonged dry seasons reduce agricultural productivity and pasture availability. These climate-induced stresses force herders to migrate southward in search of pasture and water, often bringing them into direct competition with sedentary farming communities. This interaction increases the likelihood of disputes over land use, crop destruction, water points, and grazing routes. Environmental Scarcity Theory is particularly relevant to this study because farmer–herder conflicts in Omala LGA are largely driven by competition over land and water resources, which are increasingly scarce due to climate variability and environmental degradation.

Abbass (2012) empirically showed that climate change–induced desertification reduces grazing land, forcing herder migration and intensifying violent conflicts with farmers in northern Nigeria. Using survey and field observations, Abbass (2012) found that climate-induced desertification drives pastoral migration, intensifying competition over land and escalating farmer–herder violence in northern Nigeria. The study concluded that Climate change–induced environmental degradation significantly intensifies farmer–herder conflict by increasing competition over scarce land and water resources. The study recommended that policies promote sustainable land management and regulated grazing routes to reduce resource competition and prevent conflict.

The findings of these studies showed the connection between climate change and the farmer–herder conflict, the causes of these conflicts and the effects of these conflicts on the people where they occurred. A re-examination of the causes and effects of these conflicts has become necessary due to their persistence despite the policies to address the conflict. The people of Omala, in particular, have been suffering as a result of the conflict.

Theoretical Review

This study adopts Environmental Scarcity Theory as its theoretical framework to explain the nexus between climate change and resource-based conflicts, particularly farmer–herder conflicts in Omala Local Government Area of Kogi State. Environmental Scarcity Theory is closely associated with the works of Thomas Homer-Dixon (1991, 1994, 1999). The theory posits that scarcity of renewable natural resources, when

combined with population growth, unequal resource distribution, and weak institutions, can generate social stress and violent conflict. According to Homer-Dixon (1994), environmental scarcity does not directly cause conflict; rather, it interacts with social, economic, and political factors to produce conditions that make conflict more likely.

The theory is built on three major forms of environmental scarcity:

Supply-induced scarcity: This occurs when environmental degradation or climate change reduces the quantity or quality of natural resources such as land, water, and pasture. In the context of farmer–herder conflicts, climate change leads to desertification, drought, soil infertility, and shrinking grazing lands, thereby limiting available resources for both farmers and pastoralists.

Demand-induced scarcity: Demand-induced scarcity arises from population growth and increased consumption of natural resources. As rural populations expand and agricultural activities intensify, pressure on land and water resources increases. In Omala LGA, population growth and expansion of farmlands have reduced open grazing routes, intensifying competition between farmers and herders.

Structural scarcity: Structural scarcity results from unequal access to resources due to political, economic, or institutional arrangements. Certain groups may have privileged access to land, water, or state protection, while others are marginalized. Weak land-use policies, poor conflict-management institutions, and a lack of effective climate adaptation strategies worsen tensions between farmers and herders.

1.2. Research Methods

This study adopts a survey research design to examine the relationship between climate change and resource-based conflict, with a specific focus on farmer–herder conflict in Omala Local Government Area of Kogi State. Survey research design is appropriate for this study because it enables the systematic collection of data from a large population through structured instruments such as questionnaires, thereby allowing for the generalization of findings to the wider population. Survey research design is particularly useful in research where the objective is to obtain information on people’s perceptions, attitudes, experiences, and opinions regarding a given phenomenon (Creswell, 2014). In the context of this study, the survey design facilitates the collection of primary data from farmers, herders, and residents of Omala LGA on issues relating to climate change impacts, resource scarcity, and conflict dynamics.

The design allows for quantitative analysis of responses, making it possible to identify patterns, trends, and relationships among variables relevant to climate change and farmer–herder conflict. It is also cost-effective, time-efficient, and suitable for covering a geographically dispersed population such as Omala Local Government Area.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises all residents of Omala Local Government Area of Kogi State, including farmers, herders, and other community members who are directly or indirectly affected by climate change and resource-based conflicts. According to available population records, the total population of Omala Local Government Area is

108,402 persons (NPC, 2024). This population constitutes the target population from which the study sample was drawn.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size for this study was determined using the Taro Yamane (1967) formula, which is widely used for calculating sample sizes in survey research involving finite populations. The formula is expressed as:
$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)}$$

Where:

n= sample size

N= population size

e= level of precision (margin of error), set at 0.05

Substituting the values:

$$n = \frac{108,402}{1 + 108,402(0.05)}$$

$$n = 399$$

Sampling Technique

The study employed a simple random sampling technique to select respondents from the population. This technique ensured that every member of the population had an equal and independent chance of being selected. Simple random sampling was chosen to minimize sampling bias and enhance the representativeness of the sample, thereby improving the validity and reliability of the findings.

1.3. Results and Discussion

i. Demographic Data of the Respondents

S/N	Information	Percentage				Total
1	Age	20-30	31-40	41-50	51 & above	100%
		15%	53%	22%	10%	
2	Sex	Male	Female	-	-	100%
		64%	36%	-	-	
3	Religion	Christainity	Islam	African Traditional Religion	Others	100%
		45%	51%	4%	-	
4	Marital Status	Married	Single	Divorced	-	100%
		56%	35%	9%	-	
5	Education	Primary	Secondary	Tertiary	Others	100%
		10%	15%	63%	12%	
6	Occupation	Civil Servant	Entrepreneur	Artisan	Others	100%
		44%	28%	16%	12%	

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

S/N	Information				Total
1	Causes of the conflict	Climate change	Quest for dominance	Political Reasons	100%
		63%	29%	8%	
2	Effects of the Conflict	Loss of Lives	Food Shortage	Abandoned communities	100%
		61%	22%	17%	
3	Possible Solutions	Afforestation Policies	Ranches	Land use laws	100%
		57%	37%	6%	

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 1 and 2 presents the findings of the study. Particularly, Table 1 presents the details on the characteristics of the sample size, while Table 2 presents the major findings of the study. It's evident that several factors were identified as the causes of the conflict between the farmers and herders in Omala. Climate change, which has given birth to desertification, was seen to be the major cause of the conflict. After a careful analysis of the questionnaires that were returned (All 399 questionnaires were returned), it was discovered that 63% of the sample size attributed the conflict to the changes in climate, which necessitated the search for pastures for grazing. Although the issue of climate change was seen as the major cause of the conflict, the responses of other respondents showed that there were other factors that could be seen as the cause of the conflict. 29% of the respondents believed that the quest for dominance was the cause of the conflict, while the remaining 8% believed it was more of a political thing.

This finding aligns strongly with existing empirical literature that links farmer–herder conflicts in Nigeria to environmental degradation and ecological stress. Abbass (2012) and Okoli and Atelhe (2014) empirically established that declining rainfall and advancing desert conditions intensify competition over land, thereby increasing the likelihood of violent conflict between farmers and pastoralists. The findings from Omala, therefore, reinforce the argument that resource scarcity resulting from climate change increases the probability of conflict in agrarian societies. It also aligns with the theory established by Homer-Dixon (1999) and agrees with Blench (2010), who demonstrated that climate-induced desertification in northern Nigeria has reduced grazing land and water availability, compelling pastoralists to migrate southwards in search of pasture.

Beyond environmental factors, 29% of respondents attributed the conflict to the quest for dominance, suggesting that the crisis goes beyond mere competition for resources. This supports the argument by Benjaminsen et al. (2012) that farmer–herder conflicts are not solely ecological but are also shaped by power relations and struggles for territorial control. Empirical evidence from central Nigeria indicates that violence is sometimes used as a strategy to assert dominance over land, routes, and local authority structures. Mustapha (2014) further observes that indigene–settler relations often produce power struggles in which control over land symbolizes political and social dominance, thereby escalating economic disputes into communal insecurity. The Omala findings therefore suggest that farmer–herder conflict is also a manifestation of intergroup power contestation, not merely environmental stress.

Furthermore, 8% of respondents perceived the conflict as politically driven, indicating the role of political manipulation and elite interests. This is consistent with the findings of Fayemi (2018) and Okello et al. (2019), who argue that local and regional political actors often politicize farmer–herder tensions for electoral advantage or resource control. In some cases, failure of political leadership and selective enforcement of laws create conditions of impunity, thereby allowing conflicts to persist. Bello (2013) empirically demonstrated that weak governance structures and politicization of identity contribute significantly to the escalation of farmer–herder conflicts in Nigeria.

Table 2 also gave details on the effects of the conflict in Omala Local Government Area. Loss of life covered 61%, abandonment of certain villages covered 17%, and shortage of food supply covered 22%. The implications of these results are economic and socially related. For instance, the loss of lives reduces the manpower required to boost economic activities and food supply of the people. Most of the people who died were recorded to be farmers who cultivated food crops for consumption and income generation. Their murder reduced their contribution to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Omala. Again, the destruction of farmland by herders and their cattle has led to a fall in the supply of food, further increasing food price inflation in Omala.

1.4. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined intergroup relations and the causes and effects of farmer–herder conflict in Omala Local Government Area. Findings from the analysis of 399 returned questionnaires revealed that the conflict is multi-dimensional, with environmental, socio-political, and power-related factors interacting to produce insecurity. Climate change and desertification emerged as the most significant causes, as a majority of respondents (63%) linked the conflict to ecological stress and the consequent search for grazing pastures. This confirms the relevance of environmental scarcity in explaining resource-based conflicts in agrarian communities such as Omala.

However, the study also established that farmer–herder conflict in Omala cannot be explained solely through environmental factors. A significant proportion of respondents (29%) attributed the conflict to the quest for dominance, indicating that struggles over territorial control, land ownership, and social influence play a critical role in shaping intergroup relations. Additionally, the perception of political manipulation by 8% of respondents showed the role of weak governance, elite interests, and politicization of identity in sustaining the conflict.

The effects of the conflict have been severe, as evidenced by loss of lives (61%), abandonment of villages (17%), and food shortages (22%). These outcomes have profound socio-economic implications, particularly the reduction of agricultural productivity and human capital. The killing of farmers has not only disrupted food production but has also undermined income generation and local economic growth, thereby negatively affecting the Gross Domestic Product of Omala. Overall, the study concludes that farmer–herder conflict in Omala represents a serious human security challenge that threatens livelihoods, food security, and sustainable development.

The study recommended, based on the findings of the study as presented in Table 2, that:

- i. **Establishment of Ranches:** The establishment of well-planned ranches would reduce the need for open grazing, which often brings herders into direct conflict with farmers. Ranching allows livestock to be reared in designated areas with adequate pasture, water, and veterinary services. This system minimizes destruction of farmlands, prevents crop damage, and promotes peaceful coexistence between herders and farming communities. It also enhances livestock productivity through better management and monitoring.
- ii. **Strengthening Afforestation Policies:** Afforestation policies aimed at preserving existing forests and encouraging tree planting in desertification-prone areas should be strengthened. Trees help prevent soil erosion, improve soil fertility, and serve as windbreaks against desert encroachment. Effective afforestation reduces pressure on grazing lands, restores degraded environments, and provides alternative livelihoods such as forestry and agro-forestry for local communities.
- iii. **Enforcement of Strict Land-Use Policies:** Strict land-use policies should be enacted and enforced to clearly define grazing routes, farmlands, and protected areas. Such policies would protect farmers from unlawful trespass and crop destruction while providing legal frameworks for resolving disputes. Clear land-use regulations also promote accountability, reduce conflicts, and support sustainable agricultural practices.

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